

Annual Report
2011

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Welcome

It is my pleasure to welcome you to the Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) Annual Report 2011.

The aim of the DARIAH-EU Annual Report is to provide an overview of DARIAH's key achievements in 2011.

2011 was a transitional year for DARIAH. Following the successful completion of the Preparatory Phase project in February 2011, DARIAH moved into the *Transition Phase*.

A key activity in DARIAH's transition phase is to establish DARIAH as an ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium). This legal framework will facilitate the long-term sustainability of DARIAH.

Good progress has been made during 2011 as by the end of the year, 10 countries had signed a Memorandum of Understanding formally stating their willingness to support the establishment of the DARIAH-ERIC.

DARIAH's European-wide Virtual Competency Centres will play a core role in DARIAH. Already coordinators for each VCC (VCC Heads) have been appointed and their first meeting took place in November. This work prepares the ground for the first General VCC meeting, where all colleagues from each of the VCCs will come together. This is something that we can look forward to in Spring 2012.

DARIAH does not operate in a vacuum. So another key activity in 2011, was to try to get an overview of the wide range of initiatives and projects that are taking place in the digital arts and humanities in Europe. This work will form a basis for developing a collaboration framework extending outwards from Affiliated Projects such as CENDARI, DASISH, EHRI and NeDiMAH at its core.

So that was just a few of the highlights from DARIAH's activities during 2011. I hope that you enjoy reading about the rest.

Laurent Romary

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'L. Romary', written in a cursive style.

Laurent Romary,
Director DARIAH-EU, Transition Phase

Mission

DARIAH, the Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities, aims to:

- Enhance and support digitally enabled research across the arts and humanities
- To develop, maintain and operate an infrastructure in support of ICT-based research practices
- Support researchers in using ICT-enabled methods to analyse and interpret digital resources

DARIAH-EU Poster from DH2011 held in Stanford, June 2011

DARIAH's Virtual Competency Centres (VCC)

DARIAH will operate through its European-wide Virtual Competency Centres. VCCs are cross-disciplinary, multi-institutional and international. VCCs will deliver services for all European arts and humanities researchers. Each VCC is centred on a specific area of expertise.

One of more DARIAH partner institutions is appointed to Chair a VCC. A competent person from that the partner institution will be appointed to Head a VCC.

Henk Harmsen
VCC Chief Integration Officer

Due to the crucial role that the VCC's will play for the success of DARIAH, in Autumn 2011, it was agreed to appoint a Chief Integration Officer (CIO) to coordinate activities across all of the VCCs.

The VCC CIO is part of the DARIAH-EU Coordination Office. **Henk Harmsen**, from the DARIAH-partner Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS), who also played a key role in the DARIAH Preparatory Phase project, was appointed as the VCC Chief Integration Officer (CIO).

The first task of the CIO was to ensure that VCC Heads were appointed for each of the VCCs.

By the end of 2011, VCC Heads for each of the VCCs had been appointed:

- **VCC eInfrastructure** - *Karlheinz Moerth (Austrian Academy of Sciences, Austria)*
- **VCC Research and Education Liaison** - *Susan Schreibman (Trinity College Dublin, Ireland)* and *Marianne Ping Huang (Aarhus University, Denmark)*
- **VCC Scholarly Content Management** - *Sophie David (TGE Adonis, France)* and *Henk Harmsen (DANS, Netherlands)*
- **VCC Advocacy, Impact and Outreach**, *Heike Neuroth (Max Planck Digital Library, Germany)*

The first VCC Heads meeting took place on 19 November 2011. Henk Harmsen (DANS), Chief Integration Officer (CIO), moderated this meeting where the tasks that need to be done by VCC heads in the coming months were identified. Regular teleconferences with the VCC Heads take place to facilitate this process. This work prepares the ground for the first General VCC meeting, where all colleagues from each of the VCCs, would come together to exchange knowledge. The first General VCC meeting is planned for Spring 2012.

VCC e-Infrastructure will establish a shared technology platform for Arts and Humanities research

- Enable the sharing and integration of community-developed data and tools
- Establish infrastructure services and standards which ensure interoperability across the whole DARIAH ecosystem
- Foster stability, openness and re-usability of scholarly tools and collaborative research environments

VCC Research and Education Liaison will expose and share researcher's knowledge, methodologies and expertise

- Act as the primary contact with the Arts and Humanities research and teaching communities providing the interface between DARIAH and the researchers
- Seek to understand Arts and Humanities research practices and processes
- Promote the use and application of ICT-enabled method and tools, with a particular emphasis on interdisciplinary understanding and exchange

VCC Scholarly Content Management will facilitate the exposure and sharing of scholarly content

- Consider the various stages in the scholarly content life cycle from creation and curation through to dissemination and reuse
- Offer services and resources for the representation and management of data
- Enable the enhancement of data quality, preservation and interoperability, as well as furthering a culture of data sharing in the Arts and Humanities

VCC Advocacy, Impact and Outreach will interface with key influencers in and for the Arts and Humanities

- Focus on high level advocacy
- Assess and measure the impact and value of that DARIAH brings to Arts and Humanities research community
- Outreach to wide groups of stakeholders, and ensuring capacity and participation in DARIAH.

Establishing the DARIAH-ERIC

DARIAH is being established as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC).

This legal framework will facilitate the long-term sustainability of DARIAH.

During 2011, the key documents for the DARIAH-ERIC application were developed. These include:

- **Technical and Scientific Description**
- **DARIAH-ERIC Draft Statutes**

By the end of 2011, the following 10 countries signed a Memorandum of Understanding formally stating their willingness to support the establishment of the DARIAH-ERIC:

- Austria
- Croatia
- Denmark
- France (Host Country)
- Germany (Coordinator)
- Greece
- Ireland
- The Netherlands (Coordinator)
- Slovenia
- Serbia

The organisations coordinating DARIAH activities in each of the partner countries are:

Austria: Austrian Academy of Science | **Croatia:** Institut Ruđer Bošković | **Denmark:** Århus University | **France:** Le Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique | **Germany:** Niedersächsische Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Göttingen | **Greece:** Academy of Athens - Research Centre for the Study of Modern Greek History | **Ireland:** Trinity College Dublin, Ireland | **The Netherlands:** Data Archiving Networked Services | **Slovenia:** Institute of Contemporary History | **Serbia:** Belgrade Center for Digital Humanities

In addition, Fondazione Rinascimento Digitale, Italy, Vilnius University, Lithuania and the Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences signed the Memorandum of Understanding wishing to become DARIAH-EU Cooperating Partner Institutions.

On 6 October, in Bonn, a meeting **DARIAH-ERIC Application Steering Committee meeting**, with representatives from the European Countries which have signed the Memorandum of Understanding.

The meeting was hosted by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research and chaired by **Jacques Dubucs, French Ministry of Higher Education and Research.**

France will be the host country of the DARIAH-ERIC.

Jacques Dubucs, Ministry of Higher Education and Research, France

Establishing the organisational structure of DARIAH-EU

Once the DARIAH-ERIC is established, the organisational structure of DARIAH-EU Organisational Structure will be introduced. The key Boards within DARIAH-EU are the **General Assembly**, the **Board of Directors**, the **Coordination Board** and the **Scientific Board**. The **DARIAH-EU Coordination Office (DCO)** will coordinate DARIAH activities at European level.

The DARIAH-EU Coordination office (DCO) will be a virtual organisation based in three countries: **France** with the main responsibility of all budgetary and legal coordination, **Germany** with the focus on the overall coordination and communication and **The Netherlands** focusing on coordinating DARIAH-EU's Virtual Competency Centres (VCCs).

The first arm of the DARIAH-EU Coordination Office (DCO) was established in Germany in Spring 2011.

European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI)

DARIAH is a Research Infrastructure on the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) Roadmap. ESFRI is a strategic instrument to develop the scientific integration of Europe and to strengthen its international outreach.

During 2011, DARIAH participated actively in ESFRI activities.

Members of the DARIAH team attending the *5th European Research Infrastructures workshop for Exchange of Experiences between Preparatory Phase Projects* in Brussels in June.

In September, DARIAH was one of the Research Infrastructures selected to give a presentation entitled *Preparing for implementation: the DARIAH experience* at a workshop on the *Implementation of projects on the ESFRI Roadmap* in Amsterdam.

In Autumn 2011, DARIAH-EU was invited to become a member of the ESFRI Implementation Working Group. The main objective of the group is to support the implementation of ESFRI Research Infrastructures. ESFRI has been given the target of implementing 60% of the ESFRI Research Infrastructures on the ESFRI Roadmap by 2015. This work will be carried out by identifying both the best practices, as well as the different bottlenecks for an efficient implementation process.

DARIAH participated in the first meeting of the Implementation Working Group on 15 November 2011 in Brussels.

Communication

As a distributed Research Infrastructure, good communication between the partners involved within DARIAH will be essential. During 2011, the DARIAH-EU Coordination office has set up a range of communication tools designed to keep our partners informed of the latest developments during the transition phase of DARIAH.

DARIAH-EU website (www.dariah.eu)

During 2011, a **DARIAH-EU Transition Bulletin**, designed to keep our partners informed about the latest developments during the transition phase of DARIAH.

The Transition Bulletin was published quarterly during 2011.

Transition Bulletin 3, September 2011

Welcome to the third edition of the DARIAH *Transition Bulletin*. This regular bulletin is designed to keep our partners informed about the latest developments during the transition phase of DARIAH.

In this bulletin:

- Important dates
- DARIAH-EU Coordination Office (DCO)
- Virtual Competency Centres (VCCs)
- DARIAH partner news
- DARIAH-related activities
- Feedback?

Important dates

- DARIAH-ERIC Application Steering Committee meeting, Bonn, 6 October 2011
- DARIAH-ERIC application submission, November 2011
- First edition of the new DARIAH Newsletter, December 2011
- Supporting Digital Humanities Conference 2011, Copenhagen, 17 – 18 November, 2011
- Start of the DARIAH Construction Phase, 1 January 2012

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Steering Committee Meeting

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Time and Date

DARIAH-ERIC Application Steering Committee meeting
6 October 2011, 09:30-17:00

Location

Wissenschaftszentrum Bonn [@](#)
Ahrstraße 45 [@](#)
53175 Bonn
Germany

Participants

Name	Institution	Country
Tobias Blanke	Goettingen Centre for Digital Humanities (GCDH)	Germany
Gerhard Budin	Austrian Academy of Sciences	Austria
Sally Chambers	Goettingen Centre for Digital Humanities (GCDH)	Germany

A **DARIAH-EU wiki** was created.

This is primarily used for sharing the agendas, minutes and documents of meetings.

A range of **email discussion lists** were established to facilitate communication between the different teams in DARIAH, e.g.:

- **DARIAH-all** for all colleagues involved in DARIAH-EU
- **DARIAH-vc-heads** for communication between the coordinators of DARIAH's Virtual Competency Centres
- **DARIAH-dco** to ensure effective communication in the DARIAH-EU Coordination Office.

Towards a collaboration strategy

The wide variety of initiatives and projects that are taking place at European level makes it very challenging to develop a coherent collaboration strategy for DARIAH.

To assist with this task, an environmental analysis was undertaken as a basis for the developing a collaboration framework for DARIAH.

The resulting report entitled: *Partnerships, relationships and associated initiatives - Towards a strategic plan for DARIAH* makes recommendations as to the nature of DARIAH's collaboration with such initiatives and projects.

Here are some of the key initiatives that DARIAH is collaborating with:

CENDARI (Collaborative EuropeAN Digital/Archival Infrastructure)

CENDARI will provide and facilitate access to existing archives and resources in Europe for the study of medieval and modern European history through the development of an 'enquiry environment'.

It will leverage the power of the European infrastructure for Digital Humanities (DARIAH) bringing technical experts together with leading historians and existing research infrastructures (archives, libraries and individual digital projects) within a programme of technical research informed by cutting edge reflection on the impact of the digital age on scholarly practice.

DARIAH participated in the first CENDARI project planning meeting that took place in Dublin, Ireland on 20 October. The objective of the meeting was to prepare the work package leaders for the start of the project in early 2012. The CENDARI project will commence in Spring 2012.

DATA SERVICE INFRASTRUCTURE FOR THE SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES

DASISH will bring together the ESFRI Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) Research Infrastructures (CESSDA, CLARIN, DARIAH, ESS and SHARE) to strengthen the SSH ecosystem of infrastructures. The goal is to determine areas of possible synergies in infrastructure development and to work on concrete joint activities.

The project duration is 36 months, starting on 1st January 2012 and ending on 31st December 2014.

Further information about DASISH is available at: <http://dasish.eu/>

EUROPEAN HOLOCAUST RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

EHRI (European Holocaust Research Infrastructure) is an FP7-funded project launched in November 2010.

EHRI's main objective is to support the European Holocaust research community by opening up a portal that will give online access to dispersed sources relating to the Holocaust all over Europe and Israel.

EHRI will also encourage collaborative research through the development of tools. These tools will build on, and be interoperable with, the DARIAH infrastructure.

Further information about **EHRI** is available at: <http://www.ehri-project.eu>

Network for Digital Methods in the Arts and Humanities - NeDiMAH

NeDiMAH (Network for Digital Methods in the Arts and Humanities) is a network based on the assumption that we now have a critical mass of digital content in the arts and humanities, and that researchers need to collaborate on creating awareness and understanding of how ICT-based tools and methods can make that digital content valuable for transformative research.

The Network will work in close collaboration with DARIAH to identify ways that researchers can use digital collections and content for research through the exploitation of digital research methods and tools.

Further information about **NeDiMAH** is available at: <http://www.esf.org/index.php?id=8752>

Networking

We are in contact with a wide range of institutions that deal with Digital Arts and Humanities in different contexts. These are universities, libraries, Digital Humanities Centres, Data Centres and other institutions and organisations all over Europe.

Here is a selection of the events and activities that DARIAH-EU participated in during 2011:

Supporting Digital Humanities 2011, Copenhagen, 17 – 18 November 2011

Following the success of [SDH 2010](#), [CLARIN](#) and [DARIAH](#) jointly organised the second SDH conference, which was held at the University of Copenhagen, Denmark in November 2011. The conference was a forum for discussing the potential of digital technologies for humanities research.

Further information is available on the: [SDH 2011 conference website](#).

e-InfraNet Open Workshop, 27-28th October 2011, Noordwijk aan Zee, The Netherlands.

- Why is it of benefit to the research and higher education communities to adopt a more 'Open approach' in research and education?
- What are the implications (e.g. political, organizational, legal) of a more open approach for a (sustainable) e-Infrastructure?
- How can academics from different disciplinary backgrounds learn from each other in developing a coherent vision for (the progress of) the Open agenda?

During the workshop, DARIAH-EU was asked to give a presentation on [Infrastructure and Open Research: how flexible is the backbone?](#)

Further information is available on the event website: <http://e-infranet.eu/events/e-infranet-workshop-the-open-agenda/>